

Raimund Beck KG

LignoLoc® wooden nail system

LignoLoc® nails are made of densified European beech wood. They can be applied pneumatically without predrilling or application of glue.

Highlights of innovative features

- Featuring a warm, natural esthetic, this ecological fastener also offers excellent corrosion resistance, perfect insulation, and can easily be cut and machined without damaging processing equipment.
- LignoLoc® is the most sustainable professional fastening system on the market with more than 70 % lower CO2 emission vs. conventional systems.
- No additional labor costs because predrilling or glue are not needed.
- Also available soon with head for exterior applications.

The heat from the penetration process causes a chemo-mechanical reaction between nail and penetrated wood “locking” them together. LignoLoc® nails can be driven into solid structural timber with the Fasco® pneumatic nailer. With the official approval of the DIBt in 2020, Lignoloc® nails are allowed for use in load bearing shear wall constructions.

Company | Ownership of innovation

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